

Adapting Arctos for Paleontology Collections

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Arctos is a collaborative web-based collection management solution managed by a community of collecting institutions. This system serves data not only on all types of natural history specimens but also archaeological and cultural objects. Arctos is a flexible system, designed to be adapted to the needs of its users. In 2018, staff at the New Mexico Museum of Natural History and Science (NMMNHS) decided to migrate its biology and paleontology databases to Arctos. Containing over 81,000 fossil specimens, NMMNHS is the largest paleontology collection in Arctos to date. Prior collections (approximately 87,000 specimens) laid the groundwork for paleontological and geological data in Arctos, including the University of Alaska Museum of the North, the University of Alabama, the University of Texas – El Paso, and the University of New Mexico. As an incoming collection, NMMNHS assessed how the current Arctos data structure could be improved for its paleontological data. Then, we worked collaboratively with other Arctos users and the database programmer to plan modifications to the database. These discussions considered consistency, ease of querying, mapping to Darwin Core, and complying with laws that regulate the sharing of fossil locality data. New types of data included more complex specimen parts and relationships, locality ID numbers, biostratigraphy, land ownership, United States Geological Survey quadrangle maps, and public land survey coordinates. We continue to discuss paleontology data needs as they arise, for example, ichnotaxonomy and taphonomy. Most of these data types are more heavily used in paleontology and geology collections than in other types of natural history collections, with some being very specific to paleontology. The most significant change we have made is to modify our geology attribute structure into a new system of locality attributes. This new structure allows us to handle a variety of locality specific data in a predictable manner that will increase discoverability without de-normalizing the core idea of a locality in Arctos, which is simply a unique point or polygon in geographic space. This new structure will benefit the entire Arctos community, and not just Earth science collections.

